

Working Paper: Finances of the United Dutch East India Company (VOC), 1602-1801

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Abstract

Previous researchers have reached the conclusion that the United Dutch East India Company (VOC, 1602-1796), led to the development of modern capital financing. These studies, however, lacked an in-depth analysis of the financial data produced by the VOC's accounting records. This working paper has collected data on and provides a subsequent analysis of the VOC's domestic and colonial finances. A great focus has been given to the *capital circulation* of early stock companies. This study supports the idea that early companies were intentionally liquidated after individual ventures, and that under these companies, sustained *capital accumulation* was generally impossible. This was until the charter of the VOC, which avoided intentional liquidation in its first decades. Furthermore, this study has found that the VOC began reinvesting its profits after ~1640, which would set the precedent for modern capital accumulation. In addition, this study has also identified various documents, mainly invoices and the *ten-year accounts*—which have gone unnoticed by previous researchers—that could be used in the reconstruction of missing financial records, primarily for 1602-1638. This working paper has laid the foundation for continued research into the VOC's finances, especially for its first four decades.

Keywords: capital, liquidation, permanent capital, temporary capital, reinvestment, balance sheet, trial balance, account.

Contextual Background

Wealth inequality in the United States is undeniable. The Distribution of Financial Accounts (DFA) reports as of quarter four, 2022, 66.54% of U.S. household wealth was held by the top 10% of the population. In his study *Why is wealth inequality rising?*, James P. Smith (2001) analyzed the increase in wealth inequality during the 1980s and 1990s. Smith (2001) compared inheritance, income inequality, and capital gains, concluding that wealth inequality was primarily a result of capital gains from equity markets. Further analysis of the DFA seems to support Smith’s claim: most assets owned by the top 10% are investments, see figure 1.

Figure 1

Percent share of net worth held by the top 10 percentile since 1989 (DFA)

Figure 2

Capital with and without real estate as a composition of assets owned by the top 10 percentile since 1989 (DFA)²

² Top line: Capital including real estate assets. Lower line: capital excluding real estate assets.

Figure 3

Share of all capital assets and share of real estate assets owned by the top 10th percentile (DFA)

Figure 4

Share of all capital assets (including real estate) owned by the top 10th percentile since (DFA)

Investments and the money used to purchase them are considered *capital*. Marx (1867) theorized the “accumulation of capital”, where the value of capital increases. He associated this with the “circulation of capital”, where profits are reinvested. The modern corporate firm is at the forefront of the circulation of capital. Excess cashflow from operations will be used for capital expenditures, increasing the size of the balance sheet. This study will attempt to understand the origins of the circulation of capital and subsequently, modern wealth inequality.

Prior to the seventeenth century, the circulation of capital described by Marx (1867) was still in its infancy. At this time, the spice trade dictated economies. European shipping companies would raise capital from investors, sail to Asia and purchase spices with the capital, then return

to Europe. Once a voyage had returned, the spices would then be sold above its purchased price, for a profit. These proceeds would then be distributed to the investors and the company would be liquidated. Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013) explains the capital structures of these early shipping companies: capital was invested for only single voyages, after which, was returned to investors. The “temporary capital” of these companies limited the potential of capital accumulation; profits were generally not reinvested.

Permanent capital

Opposing temporary capital is “permanent capital”. Robertson (2011) explains that a company with permanent capital will continually reinvest its profits. Only with permanent capital can a firm consistently increase the size of its balance sheet holdings, increasing the value of the investors’ stake. Both Robertson (2011) and Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013) considered the *Verenigde Nederlandse Geoctroyeerde Oostindische Compagnie*³ (VOC), chartered in 1602, to be the first company to have a permanent capital. Furthermore Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013) found that the VOC’s competitor, the English East India Company (EEIC) adopted a permanent capital because of the success of the VOC⁴. This set the precedent for permanent capital to become the standard.

Revised research question

While it may be true that the EEIC adopted its permanent capital because of the perceived success of the VOC, it only remains a perceived success. The VOC kept its internal

³*United Netherlands Chartered East India Company.*

⁴ The EEIC was chartered in 1600, however didn’t have a permanent capital until 1657 (Dari-Mattiacci 2013). For details on the EEIC capital also see Robertson (2011) page 130.

finances secret, meaning that the EEIC only had share prices, dividends, and the VOC's physical presence in the East Indies as a reference. During 1600-1690, 55% of all voyages sent from Europe to Asia were from the Dutch Republic (Dari-Mattiacci 2013). While shipping data seems to indicate that the VOC was successful, this is only in comparison to contemporary European shipping companies. This study will attempt to evaluate the VOC's financial position across its history of 1602-1801, and subsequently any major shifts in the treatment of capital. This study then raises the question: how did the VOC's financials influence the widespread adoption of permanent capital?

Literature Review

The most extensive study of the VOC's finances was by J. P. de Korte (1984), who analyzed and described the history of the VOC's finances. However, for the sake of this study, de Korte's analysis is not enough to be considered comprehensive. Additionally, de Korte's description of the VOC's finances in the earliest years is quite limited. Only a small fraction of bookkeeping from the first four centuries has survived, relegating de Korte away from this time period. De Korte's description afterwards is more extensive but remains problematic. De Korte provides a simplified overview of the company's balance sheets from 1638-1796 in his Appendix I/A. This has been utilized by several studies, given its scope. Upon critical review, however, parts of this data are unreliable. For example, in year 1642, he cites *f*291,631⁵ as accounts receivable and *f*1,115,268 as trade receivables. In reality, *f*1,115,267/17/9 was the amount for accounts receivable and *f*291,633/5/- for trade receivables (Nationaal Archief, Den

⁵ De Korte does not include shillings and pence in his appendix.

Haag, Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie, VOC, access number 1.04.02, inventory number 4583)⁶. De Korte was confused by the balance sheet, specifically that it did not include the participants' capital. However, he was mistaken—capital wouldn't be expected to be on the asset-liability balance sheet. It seems de Korte believed that Amsterdam's 1608 trial balance—which did include the participants' capital—was a balance sheet.

In 1693, the VOC's highest managerial executives, the Heeren XVII requested the company's lawyer and *advocaat*, Pieter van Dam to create a "description" of the VOC and its history (Stapel 1927 pp. IX). This was meant to function as a reference for and only for the Heeren XVII as it was kept a secret (de Korte 1984 p.11). Over two centuries later, F.W. Stapel edited and published *Pieter van Dam's beschbyvinöe van de Oostindiscie Compagnie* (1927).

Gelderblom et al. (2012) attempted to piece together the VOC's expenses and revenue for 1602-1623 using surviving documents and estimates. This study neglected many surviving documents and was mostly limited to only two accounting ledgers. This led to the unnecessary and incorrect estimate of the [ship] GOUDA's cost in 1604 to be *f*173,472. The actual cost of the GOUDA was *f*35,723/-/2 in equipage and *f*16,801/14/10 in cargo (NL-HaNa, VOC file 7196, folio 92, 102).

Missing information

As previously mentioned, very few bookkeeping records exist for the VOC's first ~40 years. This poses a challenge when evaluating the impact of the VOC's financial success on the development of permanent capital. The VOC did not have a standardized domestic balance sheet

⁶ Unless specified, all future citations of *NL-HaNa, VOC, file...* refers to the inventory number of the Nationaal Archief, 1.04.02 access number.

until it implemented the *Generale Staat* (general state). The first surviving *generale staat* is not until 1638, decades after the charter.⁷ Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013) state that “As early as 1635 it had become clear to the British, Spanish, and Portuguese that the Dutch dominated the Indonesian archipelago...” and that only the British monarchy prevented the EEIC from adopting a permanent capital until 1657. With this considered, making any claim on the success and growth of the VOC would require information detailing the finances of the first four decades. To be able to understand the VOC’s finances, this study will compile various sources into comprehensive financial statements.

Gap

Considering that most academic research given to the VOC is historical, the company’s finances and accounting have been neglected. This deficit has hindered the ability of previous researchers to draw an accurate relationship between the VOC as a political and historical entity and the VOC as a financial entity. These studies, even if not primarily about finance, would benefit from available financial data for the VOC, such as Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013), where financial data could be used to measure the prevalence of the VOC in Asia, alongside shipping data. Future historical and sociological studies could be greatly enhanced if researchers had access to the VOC’s financial data. The archived ledgers are inaccessible to researchers who might lack accounting knowledge. Robertson (2011) also reported on the limited coverage that

⁷ In the past, a *generale staat* existed of 1638-1641, this was recorded by van Dam (1701, Book 1.1, pp. 351), Klerk de Reus (1894, Appendix II), and Stapel (1927). By the time de Korte (1984) did his research, it had already disappeared.

the VOC’s finances have received. This study will aim to remedy this issue by providing accessible and comprehensive financial information for the VOC.

Research design

This research will take the form of a case study based upon analysis of archived accounting documents. A large amount of internal domestic corporate documents was preserved by the VOC and survive in various archives today. One of the largest of these archives is the Nationaal Archief, The Hague, Access Number 1.04.02. Included in this inventory are many files of accounting ledgers (*grootboek*) and journals (*journaal*), which yield extensive financial data. The complexity of accounting, to whatever extent, is a hinderance for researchers. This is worsened by the unstandardized accounting employed for much of the company’s earliest years.

At the center of accounting are the ledger and journal. Together, they record all transactions made. Ledgers contain accounts along with their balance while journals track transactions chronologically. The VOC specifically utilized double entry bookkeeping, meaning that both sides of a transaction were recorded (Robertson, 2011).

From a ledger, a trial balance can be created. This is simply an account of all balances from the ledger’s accounts. This account shows all revenue, expenses, assets, liabilities, distributions, and equity (capital paid in from investors) that can be attributed to that ledger.

Figure 5
Model trial balance account

Debit		Credit
	Assets	Liabilities
	Distributions	Equity
	Expenses	Revenue
Total of debits =		Total of credits

From the trial balance, a balance sheet can be created. This is an account of all assets, liabilities, and shareholders' equity at a specific time. Using accounting records, this study will provide an analysis of the VOC from a financial standpoint.

Methods

*Voorcompagnieën*⁸

“On April 2nd, 1595, four merchantmen, the MAURITIUS, the HOLLANDIA, the AMSTERDAM and the small yacht DUIFJE (0001-0004), sailed from the Texel roadstead. The departure of these ships marked the beginning of Dutch-Asiatic shipping.” (Bruijn 1979 p. 1).

This first venture, called the *Eerste Schipvaart*, took the form of the *Compagnie van Verre*, the first commercial Dutch-Asia trading company, established in 1595 (ibid). Following this voyage, many trading companies, funded by investors, were set up across the Netherlands' provinces (ibid). Few documents from these companies have survived, limiting any understanding of their financing. This study has collected any available information for the capital financing of the pre-companies.

Most of these pre-companies followed the same capital structure: *bewinthebbers*⁹ would directly pay for all expenses with the investors' paid in capital. These pre-companies did not issue any bonds and were entirely funded by investors. One such example was the *Tweede Schipvaart* of the *Oude Oost-Indische Compagnie* (OOIC), a detailed account of which survives

⁸ Meaning *pre-companies*.

⁹ Meaning corporate directors.

(NL-HaNA, Voorcompagniën, 1.04.01, file 31). In this account, the amount of paid-in capital (f768,466/05/08) from investors is equal to the amount spent. This would suggest that paid-in capital was measured as expenses were incurred, rather than pooling together an initial amount of capital; investors most likely didn't know how much they would end up spending until after the fact.

Bruijn (1979) as well as the NL-HaNA, 1.04.01 inventory description suggest that the *Oude Compagnie* used returns from its voyages to fund the next equipage; a primitive form of permanent capital. This study's survey of the *Oude Compagnie*'s accounts could only find one piece of supporting evidence of this. A surviving capital account of investor Cornelis van Campen provides valuable insight into the capital structure of the voorcompagnien (NL-HaNA, Voorcompagniën, 1.04.01, file 169). Campen was an investor in the *Oude Compagnie*, who paid a capital of f70825/-/- for the *Tweede Schipvaart* (NL-HaNA, Voorcompagniën, 1.04.01, file 31). In an account for later ventures, Campen has an invested capital of f67,700/-/-, of which f35,412/10/- was from "50% of the capital of the 2nd voyage" (NL-HaNA, Voorcompagniën, 1.04.01, file 169). Notably, this was in cash, meaning that upon return and liquidation, there was a distinction between the original invested capital and profits. It also must be noted that this was 50% of the initial investment, not of the total value (initial capital plus profit). This would support the idea that profits weren't considered as accumulated capital, just money to be distributed to investors, though this isn't enough evidence alone.

The remaining amount of the f67,700 was paid-in by Campen with silver in three installments. This new capital is particularly interesting; this capital was eventually portioned between two different ventures, both by the *Oude Compagnie*. These capital payments were for

the Oude Compagnie, not for the specific ventures. Only after the new capital was spent, it was determined that *f*15,977/1/2 and *f*14,908/5/- was for the fleet of 5 ships and for the fleet of 8 ships respectively. This is now twice that the amount of capital invested was not determined until after it had been spent. It's unclear if Campen would have received returns from the Oude Compagnie as a whole, or on the basis of the specific venture.

Notwithstanding, this demonstrates that capital was thought of as the investors' expenses and immediate entitlement to returns, rather than a permanent investment which continuously appreciated in value. These pre-companies fit Robertson's and Dari-Mattiacci et al.'s concept of temporary capital as they were liquidated, nor did they reinvest profits.

The subscription: Ultimo August 1602

The VOC was to be equity financed through a subscription. The plan was for shareholders to pledge an amount of capital to invest in 1602. This pledged amount would be paid in three equal installments in the following years: 1603, 1604, 1605 (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 1; Robertson, 2011 p. 323, 328). This was eventually changed to ¼ in 1603, 1/3 in 1604 and 1605 each, and 1/12 in 1606 (Robertson, 2011). The amount of paid-in capital was recorded in Amsterdam's subscription register, see table 1.

Table 1

Paid in capital by Chamber, 1638 (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 7064, folio 74)

Chamber	Capital
Amsterdam	f3,687,415/-/-
Zeeland	f1,306,655/4/-
Delft	f470962/10/-
Rotterdam	f174,562/10/-
Hoorn	f268,430/10/-
Enkhuizen	f541,562/10/-
	<u>f6,449,588/4/-</u>

The capital calls were to function as the initial funding for the company's first voyages.

Amsterdam's ledger provided trial balances after each fleet had sailed, see table 4.

Table 2

Trial balance of the Amsterdam chamber general ledger, Eerste Equipagie (file 7169, folio 105)

Laus Deo adi 12 October anno 1604		Debit	Credit
1. For the chamber Hoorn	f115,370/11/8		
For the chamber Enkhuizen	f67,879/19/6		
For the chamber Zeeland	f71,616/1/12		
Invoice from Actrus van Voort	f5,430/-/-		
For the chamber Rotterdam	f520/-/-	f260,816/12/10	
2. Balthazar Schuylenburgh is schuldich		f548/-/-	
Hans Rogurs is schuldich		f384/-/-	
3. Tweede equipagie		f56,792/7/-	
4. Cash		f15,000/-/-	
5. Balance for the Eerste equipagie		f70,679/7/3	
6. Bonds of 7%			f377,726/5/-
7. Carrack Sanata Catharina			f12,994/1/13
		<u>f390,720/6/13</u>	<u>390,720/6/13</u>

The VOC's accountants had a strange practice of dating the header of each ledger account (along with "Praise be to God" in Latin). This practice, as Robertson (2011) also pointed out, is completely useless save the first entry. Each entry has been assigned a number for a corresponding explanation:

- 1) *De patijen vande balance in debet bedragen op folio 103*: Refers to the balance of various accounts for other VOC chambers and an invoice paid to a man for 28 stucken¹⁰ of woolen cloth. The balance for the accounts "for chamber..." is the net amount exchanged with the other chamber. In the trial balance, a debit implies that Amsterdam has given more than it has received, and vice versa for a credit. The corresponding chamber would have kept an equal account in the opposite entry.
- 2) These two entries are obscure but refer to the names of men. The entries can be traced back to an account for black and white tin on folio 33. The company bought 34 and 24 pieces of white tin respectively. Why these entries were not included in either of the equipage accounts is unclear.
- 3) This entry refers to the amounts spent for the second equipage. The goods meant for the upcoming equipages were kept as assets on the summary statements¹¹.
- 4) Amsterdam's cash account was a needlessly complex anomaly. Rather than being an account of cash on hand, the cash account functioned more as accounts receivable and payable. Often the account had a credit (negative) balance, which could not be possible with only cash (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 7169, folios 229, 325). The Amsterdam chamber

¹⁰ Provide a translation for stucken

¹¹ Under the term "*voor aenstaande equip.*".

employed a treasury committee initially composed of Dirck van Os, Louis de la Becque, and Geeraed Reynst (Robertson 2011). The committee was tasked with managing the chamber's cash, hence the ledger's description reading: *Adi 5 January 1605 Cassa bij Dirck van Os, Louis de la Becque, & Geeraed Reynst -- 99 -- f15,000/-/-*. The committee was responsible for incoming and outgoing cash (Robertson, 2011). The most likely explanation is that the committee also used their own personal funds. Probably when the committee spent money on behalf of the company, the account was credited, effectively being an entry of cash owed (accounts payable) to the treasury committee. The opposite would be true for when the treasury received money, as accounts receivable. This is only speculation but remains the most likely explanation.

This theory is further supported by the 4th trial balance which contained two entries from the cash account:

(debit) *Cassa bij [Hans] Hongress, [Lenard] Raey, ende Elbert Simons genonden voor soo velve ditto ontfangers noch hebben te Berandtwoorden — 444 — f83,478/3/5*

(credit) *van Cassa bij [Dirck] van Os, [Lenard] Raey, ende Grootenhuijs genonden voor soo velve van ditto cassa is outleendt op interest voor de 4 equipage — 444 — f3,111/12/11*

(NL-HaNa, VOC, file 7169, folio 449).

The debit is clearly an entry for cash received and the credit refers to cash lent out on interest. The bottom of the ledger contains the difference of *f77,484/19/6*.

- 5) The balance of the equipage account that was credited with equity (capital) from the first capital call; effectively the difference between the capital call and the equipage's

expenses¹². This accounting style is unorthodox and was not adopted by Zeeland's ledger, which in a more modern fashion, included both the equipage and capital call as independent entries within its trial balances (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 13784; Robertson 2011).

- 6) The liability account of the chamber's outstanding bonds, which have a coupon of 7%¹³.
- 7) This is a revenue account which refers to the *Santa Catharina*, a Portuguese carrack (large ship) captured by the VOC¹⁴ (van Dam, 1701).

Notably absent are properties and the company's ships. Throughout the VOC's history, ships were not accounted for, except in rare circumstances (Mansvelt, 1927).

It must be noted that this trial balance is only for the general ledger and cannot stand as a trial balance for the entire chamber. Amsterdam accounted for its capital separately in a capital ledger (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 7067). To address this, a series of adjusted trial balances has been created for this study. The chamber's capital ledger has been added, and the capital calls and equipages have been separated. This process has been done for the first four equipages and included in tables 3-6.

¹² For more details on this specific practice by Amsterdam, see Robertson (2011) p. 350.

¹³ The actual trial balance lists each bond individually; however, they have been simplified into a single entry.

¹⁴ The VOC was allowed to retain captured merchandise from privateering.

Table 3.1*Provision costs of the ships: Amsterdam chamber, Eerste equipage (file 7169, folio 102)*

	Debit	Credit
Chests	<i>f</i> 798/04/00	
Various items	<i>f</i> 17295/18/12	
Ammunition	<i>f</i> 78905/15/08	
Silverwork	<i>f</i> 599/07/00	
Costs of foodstuff	<i>f</i> 4587/05/04	
Shipbuilding tools	<i>f</i> 2100/13/12	
To purchase the ship of Broer Sijmons: HOF VAN HOLLAND	<i>f</i> 11325/00/00	
To purchase the ship: GELDERLAND	<i>f</i> 13600/00/00	
Hemp and ropework	<i>f</i> 47729/09/06	
Sails, sailcloth, and similar	<i>f</i> 17538/03/06	
Cost of artillery and ammunition for war	<i>f</i> 2108/10/04	
Wood to build the ships	<i>f</i> 73675/00/00	
Firewood	<i>f</i> 1258/12/00	
To purchase the jacht: DUIFJE	<i>f</i> 2200/00/00	
Blockwork	<i>f</i> 1573/01/08	
Rent to lighters to transport goods to Texel	<i>f</i> 1111/12/00	
Horsehair-cloth flags and similar	<i>f</i> 307/16/00	
sloepen schuijten ende bocx	<i>f</i> 1410/13/00	
Tin & copperwork	<i>f</i> 1942/07/04	
Foodstuff supply	<i>f</i> 114672/06/06	
Cobbled stone	<i>f</i> 660/00/00	
Stone to blast	<i>f</i> 873/12/00	
Books and writing tools	<i>f</i> 1004/15/08	
Material to build the ships	<i>f</i> 15469/10/08	
Cost of materials	<i>f</i> 306/00/00	
Fustage	<i>f</i> 12878/15/12	
Various ship needs and tools	<i>f</i> 6627/00/00	
Ironwork to build the ships	<i>f</i> 34025/14/02	
Costs for the ships	<i>f</i> 12063/04/04	
Surgeon and barber's chest with medicine	<i>f</i> 1900/06/02	
Labor wages paid to build the ships	<i>f</i> 43291/09/02	
Payments to shipmasters for crew	<i>f</i> 599/05/00	
To purchase the ship: GOUDA	<i>f</i> 35723/00/02	
Sent to the chamber Zeeland	<i>f</i> 234/00/00	
Tweede equipage		<i>f</i> 50000/00/00
Sent to the chamber Hoorn		<i>f</i> 700/00/00
Ship provisions for the Eerste equipage		<i>f</i> 509696/07/14
	<u><i>f</i>560396/07/14</u>	<u><i>f</i>560396/07/14</u>

Table 3.2*Equipage costs: Amsterdam chamber, Eerste equipage (file 7169, folio 104)*

	Debit	Credit
Cost of the envoy of the king of Aceh	<i>f</i> 5329/16/12	
Ship provisions for the Eerste equipage	<i>f</i> 509696/07/14	
GEÜNIEERDE PROVINCIEËN	<i>f</i> 67343/01/12	
GELDERLAND	<i>f</i> 70220/10/04	
HOFF VAN HOLLAND	<i>f</i> 142312/12/08	
DELFT	<i>f</i> 33245/12/00	
AMSTERDAM	<i>f</i> 79815/17/10	
DUIFJE	<i>f</i> 3316/08/00	
GOUDA	<i>f</i> 16801/14/10	
Intrest paid on participants' deposits	<i>f</i> 24687/13/01	
General expenses for this equipage	<i>f</i> 19978/15/00	
Provision for the Heeren XVII (1%)	<i>f</i> 20310/00/00	
Cost of the Eerste equipage		<i>f</i> 993058/09/07
	<u><i>f</i>993058/09/07</u>	<u><i>f</i>993058/09/07</u>

Table 3.3*Adjusted trial balance: Amsterdam chamber, 1604 (file 7169, folios 99,104,105)*

	Debit	Credit
Cash debit	f1005634/14/01	
Capital recievable	f2752459/03/12	
Paid to Balthazar Schuylenburgh for black tin	f548/00/00	
Paid to Hans Rogurs for black tin	f384/00/00	
For the chamber Hoorn	f115370/11/08	
For the chamber Enkhuizen	f67879/19/06	
For the chamber Zeeland	f71616/01/12	
Paid to Artus vande voorde for 28 pieces of wool cloth	f5430/00/00	
For the chamber Rotterdam	f520/00/00	
Cost of the Eerste equipage	f993058/09/07	
Tweede equipage	f50000/00/00	
Silverwork for the second equipage	f65/05/00	
Wood for the second equipage	f6256/00/00	
Books and writing tools for the second equipage	f471/02/00	
Written-off capital	f76/14/00	
Cash credit		f1004134/14/01
Bonds		f377726/05/00
Revenue for capturing the Portugese carrack Santa Catharina		f12994/01/13
Capital		f3674915/00/00
	<u>f5069770/00/14</u>	<u>f5069770/00/14</u>

Table 4.1*Provision costs of the ships: Amsterdam chamber, Tweede equipage (file 7169, folio 232)*

	Debit	Credit
Wood to build the ships	<i>f</i> 25112/18/00	
Ironwork to build the ships	<i>f</i> 27747/06/10	
Material to build the ships	<i>f</i> 24163/13/00	
Blockwerck	<i>f</i> 2354/05/12	
Cannabis and ropework	<i>f</i> 63995/12/10	
chaloupen, bocx, and schuyten	<i>f</i> 2658/11/00	
Sails, sailcloth, and similar	<i>f</i> 23495/17/14	
Labor wages paid to build the ships	<i>f</i> 12345/18/07	
Kooyuts gereetschap for 2nd equipage	<i>f</i> 4173/13/00	
Shipbuilding tools	<i>f</i> 2097/00/04	
Silverwork	<i>f</i> 937/10/00	
Surgeon and barber's chest with medicine	<i>f</i> 1918/13/00	
Chests	<i>f</i> 1533/00/00	
Ammunition	<i>f</i> 137131/15/14	
Material to build the ships	<i>f</i> 24293/11/00	
Hard bread	<i>f</i> 44392/01/11	
Pottage	<i>f</i> 10248/16/12	
Dry and wet fish	<i>f</i> 8919/14/06	
Wine	<i>f</i> 53317/09/14	
Beer	<i>f</i> 4493/09/04	
Oil	<i>f</i> 16570/16/00	
Butter	<i>f</i> 11341/19/00	
Cheese	<i>f</i> 7757/14/13	
vettewarie	<i>f</i> 9670/08/08	
Vases	<i>f</i> 18886/04/11	
Speck	<i>f</i> 11801/10/10	
Fustage	<i>f</i> 22908/08/14	
To purchase the ship: NASSAU "with dependents"	<i>f</i> 9193/09/08	
To purchase the ship: WITTE LEEUW	<i>f</i> 15000/00/00	
To purchase the ship: MAURITUS	<i>f</i> 23500/00/00	
To purchase the ship: ZWARTE LEEUW	<i>f</i> 14640/00/00	
Den Admiral Cornelis Matelief de Jonge	<i>f</i> 1645/00/00	
Tweede equipage		<i>f</i> 660779/10/02
	<u><i>f</i>660779/10/02</u>	<u><i>f</i>660779/10/02</u>

Table 4.2*Equipage costs: Amsterdam chamber, Tweede equipage (file 7169, folio 232)*

	Debit	Credit
Tweede equipage from Eerste equipage account	<i>f50000/00/00</i>	
Silverwork	<i>f65/05/00</i>	
Wood	<i>f6256/00/00</i>	
Books and writing tools	<i>f471/02/00</i>	
Interest paid on bonds	<i>f19149/10/12</i>	
Interest paid on participants' deposits	<i>f18936/19/00</i>	
Running and general fees	<i>f34889/07/14</i>	
Costs for the GOUDA of the Eerste equipage	<i>f691/12/12</i>	
Eerste equipage for the Tweede equipage account	<i>f701/14/14</i>	
ORANIJE	<i>f141000/00/00</i>	
ZWARTE LEEU	<i>f47000/00/00</i>	
NASSAU	<i>f80742/06/03</i>	
MARITUS	<i>f141000/00/00</i>	
WITTEN LEEU	<i>f18800/00/00</i>	
GROTE ZON	<i>f78582/14/15</i>	
MIDDELBURG	<i>f117500/00/00</i>	
For Admiral Cornelis Matelief de Jonge	<i>f115/19/00</i>	
Tweede equipage	<i>f660779/10/02</i>	
Provision for the Heeren XVII (1%)	<i>f21000/00/00</i>	
Cost of the Tweede equipage		<i>f1437682/02/08</i>
	<u><i>f1437682/02/08</i></u>	<u><i>f1437682/02/08</i></u>

Table 4.3*Adjusted trial balance: Amsterdam chamber, 1605 (file 7169, folios 229,232,234-235)*

	Debit	Credit
Cash debit	f1884189/00/00	
Capital recievable	f1531739/14/04	
Simon Jans Fortuijn	f15000/00/00	
For the chamber Enkhuizen	f5418/00/02	
For the chamber Hoorn	f29500/06/15	
For the chamber Rotterdam	f84283/07/06	
For the chamber Delft	f17351/05/08	
Invoice paid to Artus vande voorde for 28 pieces of wool cloth	f5430/00/00	
Paid to Balthazar Schuylenburgh for black tin	f548/00/00	
Paid to Hans Rogurs for black tin	f384/00/00	
Geertruyt wegenaerts	f300/00/00	
Geeraerd Reijnst	f200/00/00	
Cassa bij van O's beque en Reinst voor rekeninge	f133/16/14	
Jan Poppen voor Rekeninge	f1200/00/00	
maentgelden vant schip thof van Hollant	f12000/00/00	
Hendrick Reijnst	f594/04/12	
De Rekeninge vant schip NASSAU	f502/06/02	
Cost of the Eerste equipage	f993058/09/07	
Cost of the Tweede equipage	f1437682/02/08	
wages 3rd equipage	f9420/06/07	
amoutie 3rd equipage	f20885/03/04	
tintinago	f5147/00/00	
hennip ende touwwerck for the 3rd equip	f20688/02/10	
ijzerwerck for the 3rd equipage	f2939/15/10	
material for the 3rd equipage	f2196/17/10	
houdt for the 3rd equipage	f23063/11/00	
Written-off capital	f76/14/00	
Cash credit		f2005510/13/12
Bonds		f407591/05/00
Cash by van Os		f3111/12/11
Ammunition of 9 metaelen stucken bought on credit		f1000/00/00
Comp. 14 ships		f11803/13/00
carague St. Catharina		-
Capital		f3674915/00/00
	<u>f6103932/04/07</u>	<u>f6103932/04/07</u>

Table 5.1*Provision costs of the ships: Amsterdam chamber, Derde equipage (file 7169, folio 343)*

	Debit	Credit
Wood to build the ships	f31198/02/12	
Ijzerwerk to build the ships	f28583/07/11	
Material to build the ships	f15137/10/14	
Blockwerck to build the ships	f1096/18/00	
Wages to build the ships	f30679/01/03	
Hemp & touwwerck to build the ships	f41133/04/15	
Sails & saildock to build the ships	f12562/09/08	
chaloupen, bocx, and schuyten	f1772/08/00	
Verscheiden	f5503/11/10	
Kooyuts	f2446/10/04	
Stuermans gereetschap	f1285/00/00	
Silverwork	f403/13/00	
Chirurgijns ende barbiers kisten	f2076/19/12	
Bootsman ende Stuermans Kisten	f474/04/00	
Ammunition	f66983/03/06	
Maenthueren for ships	f10629/05/00	
Broot for the provision of the ships	f15688/10/06	
Pottage	f3846/17/00	
Drooge ende natte visch	f4084/06/06	
Wijn	f23521/07/00	
Beer	f2200/06/00	
olije	f4464/00/00	
vettewarie	f4725/03/00	
Butter	f4596/03/12	
Kaes	f2468/13/08	
vleijs	f10348/09/02	
Speck	f5358/06/12	
Fustage	f10554/05/12	
Chamber Zeeland	f4589/10/08	
Purchased ship: BANTAM	f35280/00/00	
Scheepsgelt	f705/00/00	
Derde equipage		f384396/09/01
	<u>f384396/09/01</u>	<u>f384396/09/01</u>

Table 5.2*Equipage costs: Amsterdam chamber, Derde equipage (file 7169, folio 344)*

	Debit	Credit
Derde equipage	<i>f</i> 384396/09/01	
BANDA	<i>f</i> 65924/19/04	
BANTAM	<i>f</i> 124627/10/12	
CEYLON	<i>f</i> 177036/02/12	
Interesten aen Participanten	<i>f</i> 30051/04/03	
Interesten van Penningen op deposito gelicht	<i>f</i> 14124/11/06	
Loopende	<i>f</i> 16132/05/01	
Provision for the Heeren XVII	<i>f</i> 17853/10/00	
Cost of the Derde equipage		<i>f</i> 830146/12/07
	<u><i>f</i>830146/12/07</u>	<u><i>f</i>830146/12/07</u>

Table 5.3

Adjusted trial balance: Amsterdam chamber, 1606 (file 7169, folios 325,344,345)

	Debit	Credit
Cash	<i>f</i> 1571755/17/08	
Capital recievable	<i>f</i> 314370/16/07	
Zeeland	<i>f</i> 94106/00/03	
Delft	<i>f</i> 13668/13/08	
Rotterdam	<i>f</i> 86548/15/06	
Hoorn	<i>f</i> 42345/02/15	
Enkhuizen	<i>f</i> 8846/07/10	
Admiralty stadt	<i>f</i> 50000/00/00	
Jan Abeels	<i>f</i> 423/00/00	
Cash by van Os	<i>f</i> 133/16/14	
Jan Popper	<i>f</i> 1200/00/00	
Jan Pellecoorne	<i>f</i> 50/00/00	
Simon Janssz Fortuijn	<i>f</i> 3902/00/08	
Eerste equipage	<i>f</i> 993058/09/07	
Tweede equipage	<i>f</i> 1437682/02/08	
Derde equipage	<i>f</i> 830146/12/07	
Written-off capital	<i>f</i> 76/14/00	
Accounts payable		<i>f</i> 1631259/15/02
Debt		<i>f</i> 127277/07/08
Comp. 14 ships		<i>f</i> 11750/00/00
Cash by van Os		<i>f</i> 3111/12/11
Sold ammunition		<i>f</i> /14/00
Capital		<i>f</i> 3674915/00/00
	<u><i>f</i>5448314/09/05</u>	<u><i>f</i>5448314/09/05</u>

Table 6.1*Provision costs of the ships: Amsterdam chamber, Vierde equipage (file 7169, folio 447)*

	Debit	Credit
Wood to build the ships	<i>f</i> 94021/06/12	
Ijzerwerk to build the ships	<i>f</i> 30338/13/06	
Material to build the ships	<i>f</i> 18405/16/08	
Blockwerck to build the ships	<i>f</i> 2601/19/04	
Wages to build the ships	<i>f</i> 43083/18/10	
Hennip & touwwerck to build the ships	<i>f</i> 57910/19/13	
Sails & saildock to build the ships	<i>f</i> 24211/19/12	
chaloupen, bocx, and schuyten	<i>f</i> 2166/04/12	
Verscheiden	<i>f</i> 12649/13/12	
Kooyuts	<i>f</i> 4580/10/12	
Stuermans gereetschap	<i>f</i> 3483/17/08	
Silverwork	<i>f</i> 1259/18/08	
Chirurgijns ende barbiers kisten	<i>f</i> 4398/10/00	
Bootsman ende Stuermans Kisten	<i>f</i> 1031/06/00	
Ammunition	<i>f</i> 82834/18/13	
Broot for the provision of the ships	<i>f</i> 36392/00/14	
Pottage	<i>f</i> 8663/11/08	
Drooge ende natte visch	<i>f</i> 10386/06/04	
Wijn	<i>f</i> 47645/03/12	
Beer	<i>f</i> 4685/17/00	
olije	<i>f</i> 10901/15/08	
vettewarie	<i>f</i> 7687/03/10	
Butter	<i>f</i> 15376/15/04	
Kaes	<i>f</i> 6951/01/15	
vleijs	<i>f</i> 36291/08/12	
Speck	<i>f</i> 16187/18/12	
Fustage	<i>f</i> 24511/11/08	
Purchased ship: HOLLANDIA	<i>f</i> 22125/02/00	
Jacht GOEDE HOPE	<i>f</i> 6306/10/00	
GELDERLAND	<i>f</i> 32578/14/08	
Maentgelden vande bootsijn op zeelandt	<i>f</i> 29251/00/00	
Verschoten maentgelden	<i>f</i> 93/00/00	
Penningen bij de beursi getelt	<i>f</i> 1175/00/00	
Vierde equipage		<i>f</i> 700189/15/05
	<u><i>f</i>700189/15/05</u>	<u><i>f</i>700189/15/05</u>

Table 6.2*Equipage costs: Amsterdam chamber, Vierde equipage (file 7169, folio 447)*

	Debit	Credit
Vierde equipage	<i>f700189/15/05</i>	
Interesten van Penningen op deposito gelicht	<i>f5118/05/14</i>	
Interesten aen Participanten	<i>f16190/18/02</i>	
Loopende ende generale ongeden	<i>f42103/00/10</i>	
GELDERLAND	<i>f4700/00/00</i>	
GOUDA	<i>f4700/00/00</i>	
GEÜNIEERDE PROVINCIEËN	<i>f94127/14/08</i>	
HOLLANDIA	<i>f117631/15/08</i>	
AMSTERDAM	<i>f94120/06/00</i>	
PAUW	<i>f58867/18/00</i>	
AREND	<i>f58876/08/00</i>	
RODE LEEUW MET PIJLEN	<i>f99279/00/00</i>	
Vierde equipage		<i>f1295905/01/15</i>
	<u><i>f1295905/01/15</i></u>	<u><i>f1295905/01/15</i></u>

Table 6.3*Adjusted trial balance: Amsterdam chamber, 1608 (file 7169, folios 448-449; de Korte, 1984)*

	Debit	Credit
Cash	f83478/03/05	
comp 14 ships	f42157/03/10	
Jan Abeels	f423/00/00	
reinst	f133/16/14	
reckening of equipage	f1200/00/00	
simon Jans Fortuijn	f3902/00/08	
Zeeland	f168378/00/09	
Delft	f69641/06/08	
Rotterdam	f325550/19/10	
Jan Pellecoorne	f150/00/00	
Stad Amsterdam	f906/00/00	
Admiralty van Amsterdam	f110796/16/12	
Loge tot bantam	f25271/03/00	
Lijnbaan v.d. oic en boot spiramonda	f661/08/04	
Various	f18903/08/00	
Hennep op de lijnbaan	f5651/05/08	
Eerste equipage	f993058/09/07	
Tweede equipage	f1437682/02/08	
Derde equipage	f830146/12/07	
Vierde equipage	f1295905/01/15	
Written-off capital	f76/14/00	
Balance in capital ledger	f5820/13/12	
Accounts payable		f5993/03/15
Bonds		f456502/04/10
Comp. 14 ships		f3700/00/00
kas bij van Os, rebecque en Reinst		f3111/12/11
hoorn		f4547/11/08
enkuizen		f44059/17/06
proviand schepen		f4489/19/02
reckening carague st catharina		f72000/00/00
Returns of the ship NASSAU		f116771/16/08
Returns of the first equipage		f245633/10/09
Kas van de retouren bij Hongres, Raey, en simonsz		f531516/07/00
de reckening van carague st antonio		f177409/13/12
kas van schip nassau bij hongres, raey, en simonsz		f79134/15/08
lopende onkosten voor de vijfde equipage		f108/00/00
Sold ammunition		f/14/00
Capital		f3674915/00/00
	<u>f5419894/06/09</u>	<u>f5419894/06/09</u>

These accounts give a valuable insight into how the Amsterdam chamber financed the first four fleets. The next section will discuss the specific methods used by the VOC to finance its fleets.

The VOC's capital structure

As a permanent capital entity, the VOC could not sustainably rely on capital from investors to fund its operations. As early as 13 August 1602, the VOC issued bonds¹⁵ to raise funds. Amsterdam issued a bond to Jaques de Veelaer with a face value of 1,000 guilders (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 7169, folio 2). The cash account was then debited (increased) with the *f*1,000 received from de Veelaer (ibid, folio 1). On 20 February 1603, the accountant increased the amount owed on the bond by *f*40/-, citing “*of interest for 1,000 gul. for 6 months passed at 8 percent*” (ibid, folio 2). This is also the same date that the chamber paid the coupon of 40 guilders, crediting (decreasing) the cash account (ibid, folio 1). Again, on 13 May 1603, the amount owed was increased, this time by *f*17/10/- for 7% interest for 3 months. On the same date, Amsterdam paid this coupon plus the face value totaling *f*1,017/10/-. The initial journal entry had no mention of the expiration or coupon of the bond.

The permanent capital of the VOC also allowed for reinvestment of revenue. The trial balance of the first equipage include revenue that the company had received from the captured Portuguese *Santa Catharina*. Using profits to fund the next equipage would lead to larger and larger budgets per equipage. By the 1640s, the VOC was spending more than *f*3,000,000 annually on equipages (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 4583).

¹⁵ The term *Penningen a deposito* was used to refer to the company's bonds.

Both these characteristics of the VOC's capital made it drastically different from its predecessors. This is true even during the first four equipages, when the VOC still had a consistent cash flow from investors' capital. The equipage costs were considerably greater than the paid in capital amounts, this is shown in table 7 with the Company of Fourteen Ships, a pre-company, as reference. This characteristic of spending more than what was immediately allowed by paid-in capital was not present in the pre-companies.

Table 7

Capital versus equipage costs, estimates (NL-HaNa, VOC, files 7169, 11349)

Equipage	Fourteen Ships	Eerste equipage	Tweede...	Derde...	Vierde...
Paid-in capital	f1,738,325	f1,606,147	f2,141,529	f2,141,529	f535,382
Expenditures	f1,737,963	f2,031,000	f2,100,000	f1,785,350	f3,254,000
Ratio	99.979%	126.452%	98.061%	83.368%	607.790%

The disparity between capital and expenses was much more significant for the fourth equipage. The 4th capital call was only 1/12 of the total capital, much less than the previous three. Even with a limited capital call, Amsterdam was able to maintain a positive cashflow through revenue and debt issuance. As early as the fourth equipage, the VOC resembled a modern capital structure.

Financial Statements

“No evidence exists to support the notion that the VOC compiled a general balance statement before [1609]. Furthermore, it is not certain that such a balance was actually completed in 1609.” (Robertson, 2011, p. 410).

The very first general balances of the entire VOC eluded all previous researchers with the sole exception of van Dillen (1927) who appeared to not understand its severity. No internal archive was kept of this general balance, the *tien jarige rekening* (ten-year account). However, as this study has found, the VOC did in fact produce such a balance in 1609 but has only been preserved by the States General. Such a document would have been incredibly valuable, yet it had already disappeared by the time that van Dam (1701) had sought it out. In addition to this, almost one year's worth is missing from the resolution books during this time (Robertson 2011, p. 377).

Records of the ten-year accounts survive in the archive of Johan van Oldenbarnevelt (NL-HaNA, State Attorney Van Oldenbarnevelt, 3.01.14). The first file (3087) contains information of the value of cargo received by various ships, various expenses, and the company's capital. This document may have been directly from the VOC itself. According to van Dam (1701) the VOC provided audits to the States General in relation to state subsidies. The second file (3088), the same document noted by van Dillen, was sent to various courts in the Republic from anonymous shareholders. Both documents are quite similar, see tables # and

Figure 6

VOC Ten-year account, circa 1609 (NL-HaNA, Landsadvocaat Van Oldenbarnevelt, 3.01.14, inv.nr. 3087)

The image shows two pages of a handwritten ten-year account from circa 1609. The pages are filled with dense Dutch text and numerical entries, organized into columns. The left page is titled 'De 10 Jaerige rekening in de rechte' and the right page is titled 'De 10 Jaerige rekening in de schulden'. The entries are written in a cursive script, and the numbers are written in a clear, legible hand. The right page includes a stamp that reads 'SINYES ARCHIEF'. The total sum at the bottom of the right page is 13326333.

Text Description (Dutch)	Value (Florins)
De 10 Jaerige rekening in de rechte	
1996036	
1200	
250000	
260000	
1050000	
0	
440000	
800000	
2003000	
13326333	
De 10 Jaerige rekening in de schulden	
650000	
200000	
660000	
740312	
800066	
800066	
9330839	
200000	
125000	
100000	
200000	
84000	
13326333	

These statements seem to be related to the income and liquidation of the company at the end of the first ten-year period. During this time the VOC was supposed to be liquidated, however because of lobbying efforts by management, this never happened (Robertson, 2011). Both begin with an entry of *f*1,996,363 referring to a previous balance from early 1609. It's likely that this was the balance of expenses versus paid in capital and returns. Overall, these statements were probably meant to show what the VOC had and what would be liquidated; ~*f*11,000,000 in assets versus *f*6,500,000 and *f*2,080,000 owed to investors with various other liabilities. Given their obscurity, the first ten-year accounts warrant further research beyond this working paper.

Generally, early accounting in the colonies has a much vaster collection of surviving documents. The VOC kept documents of *letters and papers received* (Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren or OBP) from the East Indies. Among these are general trial balances which were meant to represent the VOC's entire colonial empire. In addition, the VOC also kept invoices¹⁶ of the cargos sent to the republic from the colonies. These records begin around 1614, but however, like the ten-year accounts, these have also been entirely ignored by previous researchers.

Later on, the VOC employed a multitude of statements, namely the summary statements¹⁷ and general statements¹⁸. The summary statements were independent balance sheets for each chamber. From these, the general statement was created, simply just an extract from the

¹⁶ *Facturen.*

¹⁷ *Sommieren staeten.*

¹⁸ *Generale staeten.*

summary statements. The existence of these can be traced back to at least 1619, when the Heeren XVII reviewed the company's debts (NL-HaNa, VOC, file 100, folio 496).

The VOC's bookkeeping faced a critical issue: it was a multinational company during a time when information took months to travel. Initially, management sought to compile statements including both domestic and colonial finances, but this was later abandoned (Robertson 2011). Given this, the summary and general statements only include domestically held assets. The *Boekhouder Generaal Batavia* (BGB) kept separate accounts for the possessions held in the East Indies colonies. These accounts tracked all imports, exports, costs, revenues, and assets.

As previously mentioned, the colonial accounts have survived since 1614 but the domestic summary and general statements are only available since 1638. Despite this, would be possible to create domestic balance sheets based on cargo invoices, equipage costs, and dividends, however, this could not be done within the limitations of this working paper.

Measuring capital permanence

In finance, capital can be measured as *shareholders' equity*, the value of an investment if it were liquidated. Furthermore, capital is distinguished in two forms: paid-in capital and retained earnings. The latter meaning profits that have been converted into capital (accumulated capital). It's important to maintain the distinction between profits that are accumulated capital and profits that are only profits. The voorcompagnien made excessive profits but these were not reinvested; profits were to be distributed and the initial capital liquidated. *Retention ratio* measures the amount of profits that are reinvested versus all total profits. Temporary capital such as the voorcompagnien would have had negative retained earnings because of the initial capital's liquidation.

A profitable company with permanent capital would be expected to “reinvest” or retain their profits. This would fulfill the criteria of capital circulation, allowing for investments of permanent capital to accumulate in value. *Capital permanence* will be measured using retention ratio. Figures 8 and 9 show the capital permanence of U.S. companies.

Figure 8

Capital permanence: Profits and distributions since 1947 (U.S. Bureau of Economic Research)

Figure 9

Capital permanence: U.S. corporate Retention ratio since 1947 (U.S. Bureau of Economic Research)

As shown, modern U. S. corporations consistently reinvest (retain) at least a portion of their profits. This is in line with Marx’s theory of circulation of capital; profits become capital.

The VOC never formally tracked net income and retained earnings, only cashflows. However, these values can still be calculated from distributions and shareholders’ equity. The following tables 8 and 9 give the VOC’s total profits and capital accumulation since inception and decennial periods.

Table 8*Profits since 1602*

	1640	1650	1660	1670	1680	1690
Domestic assets	<i>f</i> 9,796,929	<i>f</i> 11,253,459	<i>f</i> 12,670,220	<i>f</i> 13,973,677	<i>f</i> 13,382,830	<i>f</i> 14,855,366
Colonial equity	<i>f</i> 8,360,025	<i>f</i> 12,427,417	<i>f</i> 12,217,145	<i>f</i> 20,708,607	<i>f</i> 15,111,097	<i>f</i> 21,168,126
Total Assets	<i>f</i> 18,156,954	<i>f</i> 23,680,876	<i>f</i> 24,887,365	<i>f</i> 34,682,284	<i>f</i> 28,493,927	<i>f</i> 36,023,492
Domestic liabilities	<i>f</i> 12,477,085	<i>f</i> 10,756,533	<i>f</i> 11,054,293	<i>f</i> 14,314,388	<i>f</i> 13,698,275	<i>f</i> 14,009,580
Total equity	<i>f</i> 5,679,869	<i>f</i> 12,924,343	<i>f</i> 13,833,072	<i>f</i> 20,367,896	<i>f</i> 14,795,652	<i>f</i> 22,013,912
Paid-in capital	<i>f</i> 6,449,588					
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> (769,719)	<i>f</i> 6,474,755	<i>f</i> 7,383,484	<i>f</i> 13,918,308	<i>f</i> 8,346,064	<i>f</i> 15,564,324
Distributed earnings %	505 3/4	802 1/2	962 1/2	1110	1320 5/6	1555 5/6
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 32,618,791	<i>f</i> 51,757,944	<i>f</i> 62,077,285	<i>f</i> 71,590,427	<i>f</i> 85,188,308	<i>f</i> 100,344,840
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> (769,719)	<i>f</i> 6,474,755	<i>f</i> 7,383,484	<i>f</i> 13,918,308	<i>f</i> 8,346,064	<i>f</i> 15,564,324
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 31,849,072	<i>f</i> 58,232,699	<i>f</i> 69,460,769	<i>f</i> 85,508,735	<i>f</i> 93,534,372	<i>f</i> 115,909,164
Retention ratio	-2.42%	11.12%	10.63%	16.28%	8.92%	13.43%

Table 9*Periodical profits*

	1602-1640	1640-1650	1650-1660	1660-1670	1670-1680	1680-1690
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> (769,719)	<i>f</i> 7,244,474	<i>f</i> 908,729	<i>f</i> 6,534,824	<i>f</i> (5,572,244)	<i>f</i> 7,218,260
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 32,618,791	<i>f</i> 19,139,152	<i>f</i> 10,319,341	<i>f</i> 9,513,142	<i>f</i> 13,597,881	<i>f</i> 15,156,532
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 31,849,072	<i>f</i> 26,383,626	<i>f</i> 11,228,070	<i>f</i> 16,047,966	<i>f</i> 8,025,637	<i>f</i> 22,374,792
Retention ratio	-2.42%	27.46%	8.09%	40.72%	-69.43%	32.26%

Table 8 (continued)*Profits since 1602*

	1700	1710	1720	1730	1740	1750
Domestic assets	<i>f</i> 10,056,272	<i>f</i> 9,768,971	<i>f</i> 13,883,430	<i>f</i> 14,400,804	<i>f</i> 12,538,862	<i>f</i> 16,263,872
Colonial equity	<i>f</i> 31,849,612	<i>f</i> 37,723,581	<i>f</i> 40,249,010	<i>f</i> 50,585,807	<i>f</i> 47,648,019	<i>f</i> 35,525,530
Total Assets	<i>f</i> 41,905,884	<i>f</i> 47,492,552	<i>f</i> 54,132,440	<i>f</i> 64,986,611	<i>f</i> 60,186,881	<i>f</i> 51,789,402
Domestic liabilities	<i>f</i> 12,452,679	<i>f</i> 13,660,226	<i>f</i> 9,697,049	<i>f</i> 10,550,186	<i>f</i> 15,608,873	<i>f</i> 22,249,948
Total equity	<i>f</i> 29,453,205	<i>f</i> 33,832,326	<i>f</i> 44,435,391	<i>f</i> 54,436,425	<i>f</i> 44,578,008	<i>f</i> 29,539,454
Paid-in capital	<i>f</i> 6,449,588					
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> 23,003,617	<i>f</i> 27,382,738	<i>f</i> 37,985,803	<i>f</i> 47,986,837	<i>f</i> 38,128,420	<i>f</i> 23,089,866
Distributed earnings %	1760 5/6	2025 5/6	2369 1/6	2590	2792 1/2	2970
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 113,566,495	<i>f</i> 130,657,904	<i>f</i> 152,801,489	<i>f</i> 167,044,329	<i>f</i> 180,104,745	<i>f</i> 191,552,764
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> 23,003,617	<i>f</i> 27,382,738	<i>f</i> 37,985,803	<i>f</i> 47,986,837	<i>f</i> 38,128,420	<i>f</i> 23,089,866
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 136,570,112	<i>f</i> 158,040,642	<i>f</i> 190,787,292	<i>f</i> 215,031,166	<i>f</i> 218,233,165	<i>f</i> 214,642,630
Retention ratio	16.84%	17.33%	19.91%	22.32%	17.47%	10.76%

Table 9 (continued)*Periodical profits*

	1690-1700	1700-1710	1710-1720	1720-1730	1730-1740	1740-1750
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> 7,439,293	<i>f</i> 4,379,121	<i>f</i> 10,603,065	<i>f</i> 10,001,034	<i>f</i> (9,858,417)	<i>f</i> (15,038,554)
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 13,221,655	<i>f</i> 17,091,408	<i>f</i> 22,143,585	<i>f</i> 14,242,840	<i>f</i> 13,060,416	<i>f</i> 11,448,019
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 20,660,948	<i>f</i> 21,470,529	<i>f</i> 32,746,650	<i>f</i> 24,243,874	<i>f</i> 3,201,999	<i>f</i> (3,590,535)
Retention ratio	36.01%	20.40%	32.38%	41.25%	-307.88%	418.84%

Table 8 (continued)*Profits since 1602*

	1760	1770	1780	1790	1800	1801
Domestic assets	<i>f</i> 12,472,043	<i>f</i> 16,206,597	<i>f</i> 14,906,637	<i>f</i> 16,472,789	<i>f</i> 20,884,860	<i>f</i> 21,333,227
Colonial equity	<i>f</i> 43,503,367	<i>f</i> 36,127,824	<i>f</i> 30,046,919	<i>f</i> 23,510,272	<i>f</i> 35,996,541	<i>f</i> 36,660,381
Total Assets	<i>f</i> 55,975,410	<i>f</i> 52,334,421	<i>f</i> 44,953,556	<i>f</i> 39,983,061	<i>f</i> 56,881,401	<i>f</i> 57,993,608
Domestic liabilities	<i>f</i> 31,854,499	<i>f</i> 31,626,875	<i>f</i> 26,175,956	<i>f</i> 96,110,527	<i>f</i> 136,820,316	<i>f</i> 139,110,037
Total equity	<i>f</i> 24,120,911	<i>f</i> 20,707,546	<i>f</i> 18,777,600	<i>f</i> (56,127,466)	<i>f</i> (79,938,915)	<i>f</i> (81,116,429)
Paid-in capital	<i>f</i> 6,449,588	<i>f</i> 6,449,588	<i>f</i> 6,449,588	<i>f</i> 6,449,588	<i>f</i> 6,449,588	<i>f</i> 6,449,588
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> 17,671,323	<i>f</i> 14,257,958	<i>f</i> 12,328,012	<i>f</i> (62,577,054)	<i>f</i> (86,388,503)	<i>f</i> (87,566,017)
Distributed earnings %	3165	3337 1/2	3462 1/2	3525	3600	3600
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 204,129,460	<i>f</i> 215,255,000	<i>f</i> 223,316,985	<i>f</i> 227,347,977	<i>f</i> 232,185,168	<i>f</i> 232,185,168
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> 17,671,323	<i>f</i> 14,257,958	<i>f</i> 12,328,012	<i>f</i> (62,577,054)	<i>f</i> (86,388,503)	<i>f</i> (87,566,017)
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 221,800,783	<i>f</i> 229,512,958	<i>f</i> 235,644,997	<i>f</i> 164,770,923	<i>f</i> 145,796,665	<i>f</i> 144,619,151
Retention ratio	7.97%	6.21%	5.23%	-37.98%	-59.25%	-60.55%

Table 9 (continued)*Periodical profits*

	1750-1760	1760-1770	1770-1780	1780-1790	1790-1800	1800-1801
Retained earnings	<i>f</i> (5,418,543)	<i>f</i> (3,413,365)	<i>f</i> (1,929,946)	<i>f</i> (74,905,066)	<i>f</i> (23,811,449)	<i>f</i> (1,177,514)
Distributed earnings	<i>f</i> 12,576,697	<i>f</i> 11,125,539	<i>f</i> 8,061,985	<i>f</i> 4,030,993	<i>f</i> 4,837,191	-
Total earnings	<i>f</i> 7,158,154	<i>f</i> 7,712,174	<i>f</i> 6,132,039	<i>f</i> (70,874,074)	<i>f</i> (18,974,258)	<i>f</i> (1,177,514)
Retention ratio	-75.70%	-44.26%	-31.47%	105.69%	125.49%	100.00%

Sources for tables 8 and 9: van Dam (1701); F. W. Stapel (1927); NL-HaNA, VOC, files 4583-4597, 7195-7205; NL-HaNA, Radermacher, 1.10.69, inv.nr. 134; NL-HaNA, Boekhouder-Generaal Batavia, 1.04.18.02; Klerk de Rues (1894); de Korte (1984).

By 1640, slightly more than all the VOC's profits had been distributed. Clearly, the VOC did not accumulate any capital during this period. It's possible that during this time, the original 6.4-million guilders capital was intentionally maintained, and excess profits were distributed. Regardless, the VOC still maintained a permanent capital, with no complete liquidation. Had the VOC been a temporary capital, then the original capital also would have been distributed.

It's worth noting that there was a significant effort to increase the holdings in Asia. The EEIC would have been correct in perceiving the VOC's colonial position. However, this increase would not have been achieved through reinvestment as Dari-Mattiacci et al. (2013). had suggested. Colonial expansion in the East Indies from 1602-1640 was offset by debt, not profits.

In the years that followed, this began to change; after 1640, profits were reinvested, and capital was accumulated. During the period when the VOC reinvested its profits (1640-1730), it did so at a retention ratio of ~27%. This coincided with the expansion of the VOC's assets in the East Indies (figure 10). From 1730-1780, the VOC remained profitable, but these profits were not reinvested. Unlike during the prior century, holdings in the East Indies decreased substantially. From 1780-1800, the company suffered a net loss of f90 million, and liabilities increased from f26 million to f136 million. By 1801, the debt to asset ratio was ~240%, the VOC was insolvent and dissolved.

Figure 10

Equity: East Indies, 1627-1801

Figure 11

Equity: Total, 1638-1801

Conclusions

From the beginning, the VOC differed from its temporary capital predecessors. Through corporate lobbying the VOC's management avoided liquidation and solidified the VOC as a permanent capital. Despite its profitability and lack of liquidation, the VOC reinvested very little of its earnings by 1640. Only after this did the VOC's colonial empire reach its height through capital circulation. This principle would go on to become the doctrine of the modern corporation. In addition to a better understanding of the VOC's capital structure, this working paper has also laid the groundwork for continued research into the VOC's earliest finances. This study should be continued to provide an all-encompassing access of the VOC's finances for future researchers.

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